

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

Data management plan (DMP)

Naive Bayes Sentiment Classification

EOSCSecretariat.eu

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	14/05/2023	First version of DMP – created for school project.

Level of distribution		This DMP is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0). DOI: [TODO]
-----------------------	---	--

Project details

Project Coordinator Principal Investigator	Moritz Renkin, ORCID iD: 0000-0002-1404-857X
Contact person (responsible for data management and DMP)	Jeffrey Resnik, ORCID iD: 0009-0005-7763-4620
Contributors	Jeffrey Resnik, ORCID iD: 0009-0005-7763-4620, Data Manager
Start date	2020-08-31
End date	2020-09-21
Funder, funding programme, grant number	
Internal project number TU Wien	

List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
CSV	comma separated values
TXT	text
...	...
...	...
...	...
...	...

Content

INTRODUCTION	4
Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data	4
Relevant Policies and Guidelines	4
1. DATA DESCRIPTION	5
1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced	5
1b Data generation and reuse	6
2. DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY	6
2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation	6
2b Data quality control	7
3. STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING RESEARCH PROCESS	7
3a Storage and backup facilities	7
3b Data security and protection of sensitive data	8
4. LEGAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS	8
4a Personal data	8
4b Intellectual property rights and ownership	9
4c Ethical issues	9
5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION	9
5a Data publication and access conditions	9
5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data	10
6. RDM RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES	10
6a RDM-roles and responsibilities	10
6b Resources	10

Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	vocab_statistics_large_20230511-171600.csv	Structured text	.csv	100 MB	no
P2	naive_bayes.py	Source code	.python	100 MB	no
P3	Likelihood_ratio_graph_large_20230511-171600.png	Images	.png	100 MB	no
P4	Likelihood_ratio_graph_small_20230511-171418.png	Images	.png	100 MB	no
P5	vocab_statistics_small_20230511-171418.csv	Structured text	.csv	100 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Large Movie Review Dataset	10.5281/zenodo.7929635 Source: https://ai.stanford.edu/~amaas/data/sentiment/	There was no license, they simply asked to cite the paper from which the dataset was produced.	no
R2	Polarity Dataset v2.0	10.5281/zenodo.7929758 Source: https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/pabo/movie-review-data/	There was no license, they simply asked to cite the paper from which the dataset was produced.	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data will be generated using python code and .csv and .png files, with software such as the python libraries matplotlib and csv being used to create these files/graphs. Additionally, these files can be reused to speed up computations by already having a large vocabulary ready, along with the number of occurrences and the likelihood ratio, allowing for a vocabulary to be provided to a classifier and built upon, instead of completely created from scratch. The original data from the .txt and .csv files is of course available and will continue to be available, but will not be changed and there can be reused with .csv and text processing software, such as standard python libraries. Tokenization occurs on whitespace (specifically the `\s+` regex expression) using a regular expression tokenizer from the library nltk. Please note the produced data is stored on Zenodo as well as in the GitHub, and has the DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7934164.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The input data is already structured as both .csv files and as directories with subdirectories labeling the data as positive or negative, along with all of the reviews stored in .txt files. I used the .txt files in my project because that is what I was originally using, and the data is the same either way, with both being provided and present in the Github repository of the project. The filenames of generated files by the program are labeled as `vocab_statistics_` with either `small` or `large` (depending on the dataset used, for the dataset of 1000 positive and negative reviews in `txt_sentoken`, this is considered the small dataset, while the dataset of 25000 reviews is considered the large dataset) along with the date and time of the creation of the document. There is also a graph which is produced in .png format which shows the occurrences of the word, along with the likelihood ratio of the word. The words and their likelihood ratios and occurrences can be found in the `vocab_statistics_[large/small]_[datetime].csv` file. Thus, the versioning of the research data produced is based on the timestamp of its creation. There is no inherent versioning present in the data, although this could be considered if the dataset was being changed, however in this case because the input data is always the same, there is no reason to create versions besides `[large/small]` to differentiate between which dataset was used to produce the data, as well as the time of production simply because it adds more information at no additional cost, and keeps files from overwriting each other.

It is difficult to determine what exactly the metadata standards are in this field, and considering the given information, all metadata was provided by the original researchers who determined the use case of the data and are more qualified to comment on the datasets meeting of metadata standards within the machine learning/sentiment classification field. The metadata that is provided is very little, largely only the time of the .txt file creation, or .csv file creation, along with number of rows/lines and other basic information in the .txt/.csv files. For example, there is no clear idea where exactly these reviews came from (IMDB, but which movies etc.), besides in other datasets, and it is relatively unfeasible to add metadata to 26000 different files by hand (especially for a project which will receive no funding and is solely for practice and comprehension purposes). However, there is of course labels of reviews and sentiment in .csv files, and reviews are named (albeit again not with original names). This is likely due to anonymity. The names from the datasets which are reused are preserved, descriptions from the websites where the data is sourced from are also used and added to. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

There is a README file in the GitHub, as well as the data being published on Zenodo in .txt and .csv formats. In .txt format, both datasets are separated into 50% training and 50% testing splits. Within each of these train and test folders are two folders, labelled pos and neg. This refers to either positive or negative sentiment in the reviews. Thus, the folder is the label. Within these folders are numerous .txt files containing reviews. Again, the README contains more information about the running of the code. This data was not named by me, but was taken from the original data, found online at sources listed above. In the .csv file IMDB Dataset, the data is simply per review with the review in one cell, and the sentiment (pos/neg) in the next cell. These cells are labelled with descriptive titles (review, sentiment), so it should be relatively clear to understand. In the .csv file movie_review, we have more columns giving more information, but this information is largely not used in this project. The only columns used are text, and tag, which specify the text of the review, as well as the sentiment of the review, again either pos or neg. However, this information could be used for example to create different folds in the data for training/testing splits. Please also note that if the .csv files are used, they will not correctly count the number of documents used for training without modification of the code, especially for movie_review.csv where each review is broken into sentences, instead of complete reviews.

Please note that to run the program, there is information in the README, but it should be run on Python 3.9 or higher, although it may work on lower versions it has not been tested. Additionally, the path to the data must be set before the program is run, and the program expects .txt files and without them it will not run correctly. This can be easily corrected by simply changing slight amounts of the source code to read lines from a .csv and use those, but the current source code expects text files. The accuracy of the classifier on the larger dataset (Large Movie Review Dataset) is 85.132%, and is reproducible every time, because the train/test splits do not change. The accuracy of the classifier on the smaller dataset (txt_sentoken) is lower, at 77.2%. This makes sense, considering the larger dataset has 12000 additional files in both train and test splits, leading to a larger vocabulary and better results. Please note that the source code for the project was written partially by instructors of a course at the University of Massachusetts Amherst, such as the names of methods and instructions for what should occur within. However, the code of the methods themselves is written almost entirely by Jeffrey Resnik, and only the original method which calls the methods to train the algorithm is written entirely by course staff. The course was called CS490A and was run by Brendon O'Connor. The dataset large_movie_review_dataset was provided in this course as well but was not from Brendon O'Connor. Additionally, the txt_sentoken dataset was found and modified to fit the 50% test/train splits by Jeffrey Resnik. Once more, this data is from an external source, provided above, as well as in the README.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: data entry validation, and peer review of data. The data quality has already been evaluated by the researchers who wrote the original paper, and thus, if we take their reasoning as sound, should be of reasonable quality, as well as coming from a source where it is relatively easy to determine sentiment for a human (especially considering the reviews typically have stars, which make it even easier to understand how much they enjoyed the movie or not). Thus, we simply cite the authors of the original papers (noted above), and presume that their expertise in the field, along with their open publication of the datasets allows us to believe that this data is of high enough quality to use for the Naïve Bayes project.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

P1 (vocab_statistics_large_20230511-171600.csv), P2 (naive_bayes.py), P3 (Likelihood_ratio_graph_large_20230511-171600.png), P4 (Likelihood_ratio_graph_small_20230511-171418.png), P5 (vocab_statistics_small_20230511-171418.csv), R1 (Large Movie Review Dataset),

R2 (Polarity Dataset v2.0) will be stored in Other. External storage will be used because I am having issues with TUGitLab, Of course, P1, P3, P4, P5, R1, and R2 are on Zenodo and P2 is on GitHub. The DOI's of each of these datasets is as follows: P1, P3, P4, P5: 10.5281/zenodo.7934164. R1 has DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7929635. R2 has DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7929758. P2 has DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7934320.

TUGitLab would be the best place for the storage of the code, as it is a well-known version control tool. However, GitHub is a publicly available resource which provides essentially the same functions as the TUGitLab, and I already had it there. I would also like to upload to the GitLab but that is currently not functioning. Thus, all source code is available publicly on GitHub, along with the DOI for the single release. Additionally, the datasets have been assigned DOI's on Zenodo, listed above (and below). The GitHub source code also has a DOI, listed at the bottom of the README. These repositories should backup data automatically. In event of an issue, there is the local backup on a laptop computer, as well as the robust storage of GitHub. Through these protections, we can be relatively certain that the data is secure, and is backed up.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
P4	writing	writing	reading only
P5	writing	writing	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	reading only	reading only	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service. There is no foreseeable situation which should require this, considering the research is finished and the code complete.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2023-05-10	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7934164	CC BY 4.0
P2	Open		2020-09-21	GitHub	10.5281/zenodo.7934320	MIT
P3	Open		2023-05-10	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7934164	CC BY 4.0
P4	Open		2023-05-10	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7934164	CC BY 4.0
P5	Open		2023-05-10	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.7934164	CC BY 4.0

The repositories used in this project are described in the following paragraph:

GitHub is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster. Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and PJ Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world.

Zenodo is a website which allows the assignment of DOI's for datasets uploaded to the website. This was developed as an open repository run by CERN which allows researchers to deposit their data there. It was developed as part of the European OpenAIRE project.

Methods or software needed to access and use data: There are no specific tools necessary, Microsoft Excel or Google sheets (to name only a few) are easily able to access and read .csv format, as well as standard libraries in python such as csv, while most modern computers can natively open .png files.

Thus, there should be no specific tools required to access or reuse the data, outside of python, and other freely available softwares.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	Zenodo	10 years	Students and general public, as well as members of the scientific community, as it could be useful if people want to provide a large vocabulary and its likelihood ratios indicating positive or negative sentiment, without having to write the code themselves.
P2	GitHub	10 years	
P3	Zenodo	10 years	
P4	Zenodo	10 years	
P5	Zenodo	10 years	

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

dataset ID	kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

Jeffrey Resnik will direct the data management process overall, with Jeffrey Resnik also responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

Additional description (if required):